

INSULIN PREPARATION FOR LOWERING SUGAR IN DIABETIC HEAL DISEASE (VICTOSA)

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Relevance of the problem: There are more than 400 million people with diabetes in the world, and diabetes is a chronic disease related to metabolism, more specifically, insulin, and it is considered one of the non-infectious (non-communicable) diseases that have been increasing dramatically among the population in recent years. Over the past 25 years, the number of adults with diabetes has quadrupled. There are many misconceptions about this disease.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, to study the mechanism of action of Victoza insulin in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus living in the city of Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan, and make a statistical analysis.

Test method and materials: We investigated the mechanism of action of Victoza in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus who applied to the family polyclinic in the city of Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Inspection results: During the inspection, it was found that there were 100 patients in total in 2023, of which 65 were male and 35 were female patients. In a retrospective review of archival data of patients, as a result of anamnesis and laboratory findings, a high rate of type 2 diabetes mellitus, ie 65%, was male patients. In the identified patients, symptoms such as dryness of the mouth, general weakness, sleep disorders, diuresis in small amounts and frequent discharges were expressed.

In the laboratory examination, it was found that the amount of sugar in the blood is on average 8.8-12.5 m/mol, and the amount of sugar in the urine is 0.5-1.5 m/mol. In 15% of male patients with diabetes mellitus, discoloration of the fingers was observed in the right big toe due to acute circulatory disorders.

Conclusion: in conclusion, it can be said that the identified patients mainly suffer from eating disorders, stressful situations in the social environment, and the patient's indifference to his health without going to the examination on time. The reason for this was that they did not take the anti-diabetic drugs recommended by the doctors on time, and that they did not go to the medical examination every month.

References:

1. Artikova D. O., Ruzmetova D. T. XORAZM VILOYATIDA HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA SIYDIK YO 'LLARI INFEKSIYASINI KECHISHI VA UNGA OLIB KELUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 3-4.
2. Bekchanov A. J. et al. Causes of death in infants born to women affected by Covid-19 disease //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 34-38.
3. Khasanovich K. R., Tulibaevna R. D., Ziyaevich T. H. DISTRIBUTION OF PERINATAL DISEASE IN NEWBORN CHILDREN IN KHORZAM PROVINCE BY CITY AND DISTRICT AND CAUSES OF DEATH //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2021. – Т. 5. – С. 82-85.
4. Каримов Р., Аvezов М. Оценка перинатальных случаев смерти, уровня и состояния заболеваний уха, горла и носа //Журнал вестник врача. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 60-63.
5. Karimov R. X., Tursunov X. Z., Ruzmetova D. T. Modern approaches to perinatal disease in diabetes in pregnant women //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 173-179.
6. Karimov R. X., & Musaev U. M. (2023). ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH AND COMMISSION FORENSIC EXPERTISES CONDUCTED ON LIVING PERSONS. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149), 1(5), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/423>
7. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рuzметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.
8. Каримов, Р. Х., Мусаев, У. М., Рuzметова, Д. Т., & Султанов, Б. Б. (2023,

- October). ЯТРОГЕНИЯ В НЕОНАТОЛОГИИ (ПО ДАННЫМ ЛЕТ. ОБЗОР). In International conference on multidisciplinary science (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 76-78).
9. Каримов Р. Х. и др. ВРАЧЕБНЫЕ ОШИБКИ В ПРАКТИКЕ АКУШЕРОВ-ГИНЕКОЛОГОВ //Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 114-117.
10. Kh K. R. et al. PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY AIRCRAFT CHANGES IN INFANTS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH COVID-19 //JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 21-28.
11. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Особенности клинического течения при преждевременном излитии околоплодных вод и принципы ведения беременных //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2019. – №. 1 (107). – С. 175-177.
12. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Фоновые факторы, влияющие на течение беременности и её исход при преждевременных разрывах плодных оболочек //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2018. – №. 4 (104). – С. 203-205.
13. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. CLINICAL PRACTICAL ASSESSMENT APPLICATION OF POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION AS A TEST FOR ASSESSING MICROBIOCINOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 1. – С. 37-49.
14. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. OCCURRENCE OF UTERINE MYOMA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KHOREZM REGION //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 489-492.
15. SA M., DT R. RISK FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PRETERM PREMATURE RUPTURE OF FETAL MEMBRANES IN PREGNANT WOMEN //European Science Review. – 2018. – Т. 1.

